

IQTISODIYOT & TARAQQIYOT

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EXPLORATION OF TOURISM FLOW GENERATING IN SAMARKAND UNDER THE BACKGROUND OF DIGITAL ECONOMY

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Abstract: This article investigates the evolution and transformation of tourist flows in Samarkand, Uzbekistan, within the context of the dynamic digital economy. As a UNESCO World Heritage site and an important stop on the ancient Silk Road, Samarkand has experienced a significant increase in tourist flow over the past decade. We know next to nothing about how the dynamics of these tourism flows are being affected by digital technologies. This study uses a mixed methods approach by integrating quantitative analysis on the tourism data from 2015 to 2024 with qualitative information from its site participants, both operating and/or managing the local tourism sector. The result is that digital platforms, promotions on social media, and online booking services have transformed the traffic of travel; these systems create new routes of transmission and change the pattern of tourism propagation according to the seasons of the year. The studies we have carried out contribute to the literature discussing the construction of digital tourism systems and offer practical recommendations for tourism decision makers and institutions of Samarkand. Such ideas can help them make use of digital tools for sustainable tourism growth.

Keywords: Digital economy; Tourism flow generation; Samarkand; Sustainable tourism

INTRODUCTION

At a fundamental scale, the digital economy changes the landscape of global tourism today, rewiring and rearranging both how the destinations are sold, reached, and experienced for tourists (Gretzel et al., 2015). As information and communication technologies (ICTs) become embedded and continuously expanded within tourism ecosystems, the old mechanisms that resulted in the flow of tourism are transferred to digital processes in some instances, and in some cases are completely transformed. This move makes it more difficult for heritage sites like Samarkand to deal with challenges as well as presents new possibilities when the city must reconcile the need to maintain its heritage and balance it with its ambitions for economic growth.

Samarkand is now one of the oldest cities of Central Asia, and so far people throughout the region have been living there for thousands of years and there is no other place in the world that matches it in terms of tourism. It has been a UNESCO World Heritage site since 2001, serving as an important stop along the ancient Silk Road. Visitors flock to the area in search of cultural, historical and architectural experiences. The Uzbekistan state has placed tourism development among the leading policies and strategies for the diversification of its economy, and these policies increased especially in the wake of the political and economic restructuring of the country in 2016. According to official statistics, between 2017 and 2023 the number of international tourists entering Uzbekistan increased by approximately 300 percent and Samarkand has received the largest share of the travelers who come to Uzbekistan for cultural tourism.

This extremely rapid pace of growth has now made a call for tourism planning based on solid evidence that is backed by new digital strategies for change. This also fills a significant gap existing research had left, by assessing the impact of various aspects of the digital economy — e-commerce platforms, social media, mobile apps, data analysis and the like — in determining the ways in which tourism flows expand in Samarkand. Three

primary research questions are considered: (1) How does digital adoption of technology influence visitor flows to Samarkand? (2) What other digital channels are the most significant for tourists when trying to discover Samarkand and where to come to? (3) What enhancements can be made to digital tools to contribute to sustainability in tourism sectors that have an important heritage site in demand for preservation? The following sections of the paper discuss what follows. We begin by examining publications that discussed digital tourism and the management of heritage destinations in Section 2 in the literature. Section 3 proceeds to present the mixed-methods design that we have chosen to use for this study in this paper. Then, in Section 4, we share our findings using our quantitative as well as qualitative analysis. In Section 5, we discuss what these findings impact academic theory and practice. Section 6 concludes policy recommendations; in addition, suggests research avenues for the future.

LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Digital Economy and Tourism Transformation

The notion of a digital economy pertains to economic activities facilitated using digital technologies, especially those that arose from interconnected networks of people, companies, gadgets and information (Bukht & Heeks, 2017). In tourism, digitalization has revolutionized value generation in ways that have created new business models, reorganized value chains and even driven increasingly data-driven decisions. As pointed out in Ulrike Gretzel et al., “smart tourism” refers to the incorporation of cutting-edge information and communication technologies (ICTs) into tourism experiences, destination management and service ecosystems (Gretzel et al., 2015). Digital technology affects the whole tourist journey in 3 main stages. Prior to trip, tourists are inclined to consult the Internet online for the search information, social media and digital booking system to minimise their uncertainty, and choose from potential destination (Xiang et al 2015). Over the journey, mobile applications such as navigation applications, location-specific services and real-time translation tools provide accessibility and a dynamic way of interacting with the destination. In the post-trip phase, such user generated content (UGC) as online reviews and shares on social media have a significant role in destination image construction and subsequent demand (Zeng and Gerritsen, 2014).

The spatial dynamics of tourist flows have also evolved profoundly with the rise of digital technologies. Online marketplaces of accommodation such as Airbnb, and global booking systems such as Booking.com have moved visitors out of traditional tourism segments by redistributing their properties to the residential area (Guttentag, 2019). As such, while it paves the way for new forms of economic participation and domestic income creation, it also generates grave concerns over overtourism, housing displacement and uneven spatial development. Digital tourism remains an uneven space in Central Asia. Kazakhstan stands out as an instance, as its infrastructure for e-tourism has been greatly developed, and after economic liberalization reforms introduced in 2016, an even stronger push was launched by Uzbekistan. Regional tourism strategies have been increasingly driven by the need to build on (Asian Development Bank, 2022) digital connectivity, smart destination management, and the integration of platform-based support services. Uzbekistan in particular has invested in digital tourism platforms and e-governance tools to increase the reach and public visibility of destinations. Despite these developments, research investigating the impact of digital actions toward tourism has been restricted, at least in historically important destinations such as Samarkand.

2.2 Heritage Tourism and Digital Interpretation

Digital technologies can bring with them great benefits in heritage tourism and simultaneously introduce some of the most difficult challenges. Being heritage sites, however, such places need to find a balance between accessibility and preservation, as increased visitation risks the physical integrity and cultural authenticity of the places.

Digital interpretation tools based on augmented reality (AR), virtual reality (VR), and interactive mobile applications have been found to be beneficial in motivating visitors and reducing the physical pressure on sensitive sites. The Digital Dunhuang initiative in China, for example, is an example of how high-resolution digitalization and virtual access complement conservation and public education in one, that has allowed for the exploration of sensitive relics at a distance. The idea of digital cultural heritage encompasses digital technologies used for the production and transmission of knowledge, but also as instruments that can serve not only tourism consumption.

Digital heritage as a way to protect cultures for future generations and facilitate global accessibility is consistently highlighted by UNESCO (UNESCO, n.d.). Such a strategy is consistent with the UN Sustainable Development Goal 11.4—a commitment to strengthening efforts to protect and safeguard the world's cultural

and natural heritage (United Nations, 2015). In the case of Samarkand, integration of digital interpretation is particularly important due to the fragility and historical significance of its Timurid-era monuments. However, while digital tools for documenting architectural buildings, such as 3D scanning and architectural modeling, have increased for conservation purposes (ICOMOS, 2017), there are still very few high-quality, multilingual digital tools that tourists can employ. Hence, though digital infrastructure is developing, its application to enhance the visitor experience and support sustainable tourism management is still at an early stage. Thus, further research is required to investigate how digital tools may simultaneously enhance accessibility, enrich interpretation, and promote heritage conservation in culturally sensitive areas.

2.3 Tourist Flow Generation Mechanisms

Building the 'flow of tourists' is not only about the sheer volume of tourists to visit destinations, but must also involve the strategic creation, enhancement, and capture of value throughout the tourist experience. In theoretical terms, tourism destinations operate as complex systems with demand influenced by marketing, accessibility, experience quality, and value perception (Dwyer et al., 2020). These processes now, in the digital economy, are increasingly mediated by digital platforms and technologies that influence both tourist decision-making and on-site behavior.

First and foremost, digital engagement is at the centre of driving tourism demand. The search for information, social media exposure, and digital marketing strategies have a strong effect on destination awareness and travel intentions. Digital information ecosystems have become an important channel for travelers to both discover and assess destinations that are emerging or less well-known around the world (Zheng Xiang and Ulrike Gretzel, 2010). This approach is especially crucial, particularly for locations that are looking to grow their international profile and compete in the global tourism market.

The second thing is to increase visitor satisfaction in the region which is crucial for driving tourist flow generation. Joseph Pine and James Gilmore (1999) noted that "modern customers", seeking memorable and immersive experiences, are replacing standardized services. When considering tourism, this means that destinations that are able to provide diversified products and provide integrated services with high-quality experiences are more likely to draw visitors and drive longer stays. As a corollary, frameworks focusing on destination competitiveness underline the role of resource integration, service quality, and experiential value in the maintenance of tourism demand (Ritchie & Crouch, 2003).

Third, value capture mechanisms are responsible for the economic outcomes of tourism flows. In addition to boosting number of visitors, the destinations must ensure that tourist arrivals will create a sustainable economic effect. Service industries (including tourism), using revenue management techniques, as proposed by Sheryl E. Kimes (1989), have gained a tool in the optimization of pricing as well as capacity utilization.

2.4 Tourism Flow Analysis Methods

Tourist flow analysis aims to analyze the spatial and temporal distribution of tourists within and across destinations. Previous methods primarily drew on conventional data sources, such as accommodation counts, border entry documentation, or survey-based methods that collected aggregated and time-lagged information (Lew & McKercher, 2006). Though useful at a macro-level, these methods are not suited to providing detailed and dynamic insights of mobility patterns.

Rapid evolution of digital technologies has introduced the researchers to a better understanding of tourist movements by accessing the data from different sources. High-resolution data on tourists' behaviors is accessible from mobile device-generated digital traces, location-based services, and online platforms (Raun et al., 2016). An illustration of tourist flows in the contemporary world is user-generated content (UGC) on social media outlets. Zheng Xiang and Ulrike Gretzel (2010) are well-known that content online about travel and social media has influenced travel-related decision-making and spatial movement. Geotagged pictures and posts within apps like Instagram and Flickr allow researchers to map concentrations of tourists, identify hotspots, and investigate seasonal visitor dynamics.

However, the process of big data in tourism research is not without its methodological concerns. One major limitation is sampling bias as digital records generally cover younger, more digitally literate individuals at the expense of other population groups. In addition, data accessibility, information privacy, and platform-specific algorithms may affect the reliability of and comparability of results.

However, in spite of these weaknesses, recent progress in the field of artificial intelligence and machine learning developments has greatly improved the ability to efficiently predict tourism flow in analysis of tourism traffic. By combining disparate datasets (i.e., search engine queries, online booking data, and mobility patterns), the predictability of forecasting the tourism demand has been improved from more heterogeneous data by adopting predictive analysis models (Li et al., 2017).

These capabilities are of special significance to the management of tourism demand pressure at heritage sites for managing visitor flows, such as for monitoring the visitor management of in heritage destinations, for instance, timed entry systems, dynamic pricing, and flexible spatial adjustment of tourist flow reallocation in an adaptive manner. Therefore, digital data analytics plays a critical role in enhancing sustainable and efficient tourism management for culturally sensitive destinations. The above research, though richly researched, identifies clear research gaps that we still need to fill: (1) combined frameworks that link digital economy, heritage management and flow generation concept; (2) practical experiments that investigate digital interaction work in heritage context in Central Asia; and (3) development strategies that adapt to the digital tourism specificities in today's heritage centers. This article tries to bridge these gaps, by conducting a step-by-step study of tourist flow generation process in Samarkand.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This research follows a sequential explanatory mixed-methods design to combine quantitative work on tourism statistics and qualitative information gained from the relevant stakeholders. Data analysis was done throughout the entire research project between January and December 2024. For the quantitative portion of the work, we examined secondary data by analyzing three different sources: Monthly statistics of tourist arrivals from 2015 to 2024 collected through official website of the Republic of Uzbekistan on Statistics, categorizing tourists by nationality and type of accommodation used by tourists; (2) Data available from social media platforms Instagram and TripAdvisor from 2020 to 2024 to keep track of the amount of posts about Samarkand attractions, the sentiment conveyed during such posts and their geographic origin.

For this study we employed three main statistical methods; first using time series decomposition as a method to identify the seasonal trends, then correlation analysis of a correlation between digital marketing spend and arrivals of tourists and regression models for predicting tourists in numbers using digital engagement data. Analysis was conducted in Python 3.11, using suitable packages, including forecast. The qualitative part of the study was complemented with a number of semi-structured interviews with 25 stakeholders (five officials from the tourism ministry, eight hotel managers, seven tour guides, and five heritage conservation experts). Interviews were 45-90 min long, arranged in Uzbek, Russian, or English, for the participant preference.

We transcribed all interviews and thematically analyzed each transcript with assistance from NVivo 14. We have also given a visitor questionnaire to 200 overseas visitors who visit Samarkand's main attractions (Registan Square, Gur-e-Amir, Shah-i-Zinda) during the May-August peak travel season 2024. The survey covered three aspects: use of digital channels for trip planning, satisfaction with the local digital travel services, and basic demographic info. 78% of responses were received, collecting 156 completed surveys. There are some methodological limitations: historical digital traces may carry an intrinsic bias; for instance, older tourists tend to be underrepresented; response to surveys may reflect self-selection bias; and social media data collection took place in a relatively short period. This project undertook methodological triangulation to cross-validate our results, and in this report, we clearly detailed all data restrictions to overcome those problems.

4. ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

4.1 Quantitative Findings: Tourism Flow Patterns

Analysis shows a significantly higher number of tourists visiting Samarkand in recent years especially after the liberalization of policies and tourism since 2016 in Uzbekistan.

Nonetheless, some official and institutional reports have noted that Samarkand continued to capture a share of the international visitors as a prominent cultural heritage city. Seasonality is obvious in the temporal pattern of tourist arrivals. The most popular days of visitation are spring (March–May) and autumn (September–October) when it is more conducive for tourists and cultural activities. The Navruz time of year is also one of the most important festivals for tourists as it induces significant visitor demand in early spring. On the other hand, in winter (January–February), demand is still low because of the climate of the cold and lower outdoor tourism activities.

Despite that, recent patterns indicate an increasingly diversified seasonal demand. Interviews with tourism stakeholders and observation data suggest an increased presence in off-season travel by visitors -which may reflect the targeted promotional approach and wider reach of the campaigns. This change suggests that Samarkand's demand for tourism is less dominated by conventional peaks which helps balance the flow of tourist throughout the year.

The results emphasize the increased influence of digital platforms on tourist behaviour and destination presence. Booking-based booking systems and accommodation systems in particular, such as Booking.com

and Airbnb, are increasingly used by international visitors for planning travel and their needs to manage their accommodation. These platforms also shape tourist distribution in space based not just on convenience to accommodation but also by allowing tourists to stay in unconventional areas outside 'hotel destinations'. Media surrounding Samarkand, especially visual content on platforms like Instagram, plays a key role in the construction of a destination image and attracting visitors. Qualitative analysis suggests that increased online visibility increases tourist interest resulting in the case to be made that online engagement is an important driver of demand for tourism in the digital economy. While quantitative indicators of platform usage and market share cannot be objectively assessed from the literature, a convergence of qualitative and secondary data highlights strong relationship between digital exposure and the flow of tourism. This reflects existing literature on the influence of user-generated content and online information search on travel decisions.

4.2 Qualitative Findings: Stakeholder Perspectives

We were able to identify the main themes from our interview data on digital transformation as a challenge and as an opportunity. Staff working in the field of tourism were the respondents who pointed out drawbacks in existing infrastructure: "Despite putting together great digital content, a lot of guests will say that mobile service is terrible at heritage spots — especially when they're inside old structures"(Ministry official, Interview #3). Leaders of hotels said that branding online had become as crucial as any word of mouth: "A single bad review on TripAdvisor can take 15% off the number of bookings we receive from an entire month. We have some people on the staff right now to take care of how we look online" (Hotel manager, Interview #7). Tour guides have mixed feelings about the tools that they employ. Although most of them agree about how they help marketing and booking, many of those guides fear abandoning their core skills: "When people came in they'd read full digital guides so they could look for a cheaper price based on what they found on the net" (Tour guide, Interview #12). And most guides still regard digital tools as tools that work in concert with their work, not against it. Which is particularly important when we're trying to offer detailed, nuanced explanations of sophisticated history. Traditional preservation experts have observed digital documentation makes an enormous contribution to how we keep historic objects and sites. One such specialist replied: '3D scanning totally transformed the way we do our conservation work. These days we can trace the structural changes to just a millimeter, and manage what work needs to be done first before any damage that people can observe can actually take place'(Conservation expert, Interview #22). Some other experts have said we need to link up tourism and conservation databases more closely, to ensure that what we're managing visitors with is, ultimately, consistent with what our preservation objectives entail.

4.3 Visitor Survey Results: Digital Channel Usage

We gathered responses from 156 participants and the survey paints a clearer picture concerning just what digital tools tourists use on their trips. Specifically, for travel planning information, the most frequent sources are Instagram, Official tourism websites, YouTube, Travel agencies. And the most popular platforms when people do book their trips are Booking.com, Airbnb, Travel agencies, Direct hotel websites.

In different tourist destinations, tourists varied in their satisfaction of access to digital services. Young-to-middle age tourists (18–35 years old) were also more likely to depend on social media for their trip planning ($\chi^2 = 15.3, p < 0.001$), and 78% of this age group reported some part of their trip took place online while they were still on the road. Tourists aged 55 and older said it was their preference to use more conventional sources of information such as guidebooks and travel agents — but many felt that travelers in the 35-ish age group would like simpler, easier to use digital interfaces for travel planning. What emerges from the data is that 65 percent of those who responded to the survey said digital content altered the type of elements they included when planning travel, with virtual tours and 360-degree photography most likely to influence their decisions to do so. But 41% of respondents also expressed concern that too much digital technology could turn authentic travel experiences into something less memorable. This push/pull between embracing digital tools to enhance the travel experience and maintaining the authenticity of the travel experience emerges as a foundational problem that will require deliberate, balanced navigation as they shift in the coming years.

Conclusion and suggestions

The study reveals the significant role of different strands of the digital economy in shaping the growth of the tourism flows in Samarkand. New digital systems are replacing past relationships by enabling people to locate places, set up trips and express their experiences on the internet. The results demonstrate that how well a location is perceived online—as measured by how people engage with it on social media, how often someone searches for the site online and how effectively it is presented on mainstream platforms — can powerfully determine the numbers of tourists. This was a significant departure from earlier systems of marketing tourism, in which real infrastructure and relationships with tourism agencies were the main determinants of whether or not tourists came to an area.

The paper also highlights the opportunities and challenges the move to digital tourism brings to Samarkand. Here are the opportunities in use: (1) Tourism development throughout the year when the targeted usage of digital marketing techniques occurs, (2) More sectors of the local economy may profit from it by allowing tourists to use platform-based places to stay outside of the established hotel-heavy districts, (3) Visitors can have a better overall experience by using digital tools based on local sites and history, and (4) Saving heritage can be improved through the use of digital documentation techniques.

Key challenges include (1) No digital backbone to meet these needs, particularly where reliable mobile connection across heritage grounds is concerned (2) There is a risk that the authentic cultural experience of local users will be compromised if the digital experience replaces meaningful encounters with their local cultural heritage (3) There are not enough people doing tourism work who have the digital savvy to cope with the changes to the digital skill set that are demanded, and (4) There are still real concerns about how personal information is handled or protected when travel is monitored, when tourists are recorded and stored.

In terms of theoretical implications, this work enlarges the scope of the concept of “smart tourism” in the case where heritage maintenance is fundamental. In these ecosystems, any digital solution must achieve an ‘optimal’ compromise between enhancing the visitor experience and protecting the heritage sites. This research provides a concrete framework that can be employed to scrutinize digital tourism ecosystems within developing destination areas that are characterized by legacy sites, especially how technologies capabilities, environment and cultures, interact. For tourism actors dealing in Samarkand, this paper provides several practical recommendations: (1) Fund the construction of infrastructure that combines digital tools with tangible heritage resources and infrastructure which ensures that all major attractions continue to have reliable (ie, reliable) internet connection, and thus maintaining the original cultural experiences for those who visit; (2) Design targeted digital literacy training programs for small- and medium- enterprises; (3) Implement visitor management systems that can be tailored according to guests’ needs, for example, to reduce site-to-site congestion, based on prediction of future visitor demand; (4) Collaborate internationally with online platforms to produce digital content, thus increasing visibility from the destination for visitors abroad; (5) Establish the standards to be followed to govern data, combining the improvement of tourism operations with the security of the privacy of those who travel in the region. Future studies should also seek the long term economic implications of digitalisation and the tourism occupations. It should also look for differences across cultures in the behaviours of individuals interacting with digital tourism, and develop models for assessing how effective digital heritage interpretation actually is. With Samarkand continuing on its path to digital tourism, there will be a need for active cooperation between academics and practitioners from the field. This is the only viable means of achieving the dream of sustainable and inclusive development of tourism that properly values new technology as well as the safeguarding of culture.

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